

Inland Waters

The future of temporary wetlands in drylands under the global change.

--Manuscript Draft--

Full Title:	The future of temporary wetlands in drylands under the global change.
Manuscript Number:	TINW-2020-0096R1
Article Type:	Special Issue
Keywords:	Temporary wetlands; egg-seed bank; biodiversity hotspot; resilience; water quality; trophic web
Abstract:	<p>The Andalusian International University held a Workshop entitled 'Temporary wetlands' future in drylands under the projected global change scenario' in March 2020 in Baeza, Spain, with 26 participants from 10 countries. The workshop objectives were to promote international cooperation and scientific exchange on the conservation and protection of temporary wetlands. The participants highlighted the extreme conditions that temporary and permanent wetlands, ponds and shallow lakes are currently facing, foreseeing a dismal future due to climate change. To foster a holistic view of these ecosystems, the workshop focused on wetlands including their watersheds. It was concluded that the main threats include those affecting water quality and quantity as well as those affecting egg-seed banks, species population dynamics, and trophic web features. Moreover, the inherent characteristics of water bodies in drylands and their general high resilience and resistance to harsh conditions are already negatively impacted by direct human actions and climate change. Another threat is the time lag between the issuing of scientific warnings and the social and political concern leading to mitigating actions. Thus, more effective actions to protect and conserve temporary wetlands are essential. Research networks could help propel the needed conservation actions, but the global recession due to the COVID-19 pandemic will pose a challenge as economies are burdened with urgent expenses. This special issue of the journal <i>Inland Waters</i> is the result of the workshop presentations and includes an overview on the topics discussed.</p>
Order of Authors:	<p>Gema Parra</p> <p>Francisco Guerrero</p> <p>Javier Armengol</p> <p>Luc Brendonck</p> <p>Sandra Brucet</p> <p>Max Finlayson</p> <p>Luciana Gomes-Barbosa</p> <p>Patrick Grillas</p> <p>Erik Jeppesen</p> <p>Fernando Ortega</p> <p>Rafael Vega</p> <p>Tamar Zohary</p>
Response to Reviewers:	<p>The manuscript has been updated with the references that have been already accepted in the Special Issue. However, several articles are still under the review process. We hope the final list can be updated soon.</p> <p>We have added a figure to make more clear the connexion among the thematic blocks.</p>

1 **The future of temporary wetlands in drylands under global change**

2

3 **Gema Parra¹, Francisco Guerrero¹, Javier Armengol², Luc Brendonck^{3,4}, Sandra**

4 **Brucet^{5, 6}, C. Max Finlayson⁷, Luciana Gomes-Barbosa⁸, Patrick Grillas⁹, Erik**

5 **Jeppesen^{10,11,12,13}, Fernando Ortega¹, Rafael Vega¹⁴, Tamar Zohary¹⁵**

6 1. Animal Biology, Plant Biology and Ecology Department. Centre for Advanced

7 Studies in Earth, Energy and Environmental Sciences. University of Jaén. 23071 Jaén.

8 Spain

9 2 Microbiology and Ecology Department/ICBiBE. University of Valencia. Spain

10 3 Animal Ecology, Global Change and Sustainable Development. KU Leuven. Charles

11 Deberiotstraat 32. B-3000 Leuven, Belgium.

12 4. Water Research Group, Unit for Environmental Sciences, and Management, North-

13 West University, Private Bag X6001, Potchefstroom 2520, South Africa

14 5 Aquatic Ecology Group, University of Vic – Central University of Catalonia, Vic,

15 Spain.

16 6 Catalan Institution for Research and Advanced Studies, ICREA, Barcelona, Spain

17 7 Institute for Land, Water & Society, Charles Sturt University, Albury, NSW 2640,

18 Australia

19 8 Departamento de Fitotecnia e Ciências Ambientais, Universidade Federal da Paraíba,

20 Areia, Brazil

21 9 Tour du Valat – Research Institute for the Conservation of Mediterranean wetlands.

22 Le Sambuc – 13200 Arles France

23 10 Department of Bioscience, Aarhus University, Silkeborg 8600, Denmark

24 11 Sino-Danish Centre for Education and Research, Beijing 100049, China

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
- 25 12 Limnology Laboratory, Department of Biological Sciences and Centre for
26 Ecosystem Research and Implementation, Middle East Technical University, Ankara
27 06800, Turkey
28 13 Institute of Marine Sciences, Middle East Technical University, Mersin 33731,
29 Turkey
30 14 University of Cordoba, Geography Studies Research Group, Plaza del Cardenal
31 Salazar, 3, 14003, Córdoba, Spain
32 15 Kinneret Limnological Laboratory. Israel Oceanographic & Limnological Research.
33 Box 447 Migdal 14950. Israel

36

37 Abstract

38 The Andalusian International University held a Workshop entitled *Temporary wetlands'*

39 *future in drylands under the projected global change scenario* in March 2020 in Baeza,

40 Spain, with 26 participants from 10 countries. The workshop objectives were to

41 promote international cooperation and scientific exchange on the conservation and

42 protection of temporary wetlands. The participants highlighted the extreme conditions

43 that temporary and permanent wetlands, ponds and shallow lakes are currently facing,

44 ~~foreseeing~~ a dismal future due to climate change. To foster a holistic view of these

45 ecosystems, the workshop ~~focused on wetlands including their~~ watersheds. It was

46 concluded that the main threats ~~include~~ those affecting water quality and quantity as

47 well as ~~those affecting~~ egg-seed banks, species population dynamics, and ~~trophic web~~

48 ~~features~~. Moreover, the inherent characteristics of water bodies in drylands ~~and their~~

49 ~~general~~ high resilience and resistance to harsh conditions are already negatively

50 impacted by direct human actions and climate change. Another threat is the time lag

51 between ~~the issuing of~~ scientific warnings and the social and political concern leading to

52 mitigating actions. Thus, more effective actions to protect and conserve temporary

53 wetlands are essential. Research networks could help ~~propel~~ the ~~needed~~ conservation

54 actions, but the global recession due to the COVID-19 pandemic will pose a challenge

55 as economies are burdened with urgent expenses. This special **issue** of the journal

56 *Inland Waters* is the result of the workshop presentations and ~~includes an overview on~~

57 ~~the topics discussed.~~

58

59

60 **Keywords:** Temporary ponds, egg-seed banks, biodiversity hotspot, resilience, water

61 quality, trophic web.

62

63 **Temporary wetlands in drylands**

64 Under global change scenarios, water shortages in drylands are projected to increase
65 due to population increase, land use changes and declining precipitation (IPCC 2014).

66 From 1960 to 2000, the global use of fresh water (drylands included) expanded at a
67 mean rate of 25% per decade (MEA, 2005). Consequently, we can expect increased
68 pressure on aquatic ecosystems and aquifers for supplying more water, with negative
69 impacts on the water regimes and biota of the wetlands (Brendonck et al. 2015, Kneitel
70 2016, Zadereev et al. 2020, Yilmaz et al. 2021). The wetlands encompass diverse types,
71 including endorheic water bodies, from tiny ponds to large chotts or sebkhas, but also
72 temporarily flooded margins of permanent bodies such as streams and lakes. In the
73 following, we use the term “wetlands” in a general sense to include marshes and
74 swamps, as well as ponds and shallow lakes in drylands.

75 Although wetland ecosystems are among the most threatened globally (MEA 2005), they
76 support a high species richness, including the dormant components (egg and seed bank)
77 of many communities (Brendonck and De Meester 2003, Brock 2011), making them a
78 significant part of global biodiversity (Williams 2006). Additionally, they provide
79 habitats for many animals, including nesting and feeding birds, and plants. Although the
80 general public has little awareness of the existence of wetlands, these aquatic
81 ecosystems have gained increased attention in different countries after they became
82 contracting parties to the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands. The resulting reports and
83 studies published during the past ca. 50 years on the sustainable use of different types of
84 wetlands and the services that they provide have increased the awareness of their need
85 for protection. This includes Resolution VIII.33 (Ramsar 2002) that highlights
86 temporary wetlands as “Wetlands of International Importance”. This increasing

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

87 understanding of the value of these ecosystems by conservationists stands in stark
88 contrast to the overall disinterest displayed by policy and decision makers who largely
89 fail to recognise the importance of these ecosystems (Ramsar Convention on Wetlands
90 2018).

91 Hydrological characteristics (duration, depth and their variations within and between
92 years) are amongst the main factors influencing the ecological functioning of wetlands
93 (Keddy 2000, Brendonck et al. 2015, 2017). But land use changes, agricultural
94 intensification and other indirect global impacts have become common drivers of
95 change in drylands (Yılmaz, 2021). The existence of lag time between the identification
96 of issues by scientists and the social and political responses is another identified threat.
97 For that reason, new or better regulation and management planning, based on scientific
98 information, are essential, as discussed at the workshop.

99 Our objective with this paper is to summarise the conclusions of the workshop
100 *Temporary wetlands' future in drylands under the projected global change scenario'*
101 held by The Andalusian International University in March 2020 and of the papers
102 presented in this special issue. Five thematic blocks were highlighted to give a general
103 picture of the present and future conditions and the challenges faced by temporary
104 wetlands. The themes included were: (i) water quantity and quality; (ii) egg and seed
105 banks; (iii) ecological resilience; (iv) role of trophic web maintenance and (v) role of
106 temporary wetlands as hotspots of biodiversity. We acknowledge, of course, that issues
107 not treated at the workshop, such as invasive species, may be of importance as well.
108 Each thematic block maintains connections with the rest, as a characteristic feature of
109 complex systems, which must lead to the explore for complex solutions too (Figure 1).

111 **Water quantity and quality**

112 Changes in precipitation and evapotranspiration patterns due to climate change (IPCC
113 2014) have in some areas increased the duration of dry periods (Döll and Zhang 2010)
114 with major implications for small aquatic ecosystems (Rosset et al. 2010; Tuytens et al.
115 2014; Pinceel et al. 2018). They are also threatened directly (i.e., agriculture; MEA
116 2005) and indirectly by various human activities and pressures (i.e., global change;
117 Phillips et al. 2015). Global change has already affected the duration and extent of
118 flooding of existing temporary water bodies and some previously permanent water
119 bodies have now become temporary (Yılmaz et al. 2021). Shorter hydroperiod lengths,
120 as a consequence of reduction in rainfall, and higher temperature result in shortened
121 growing seasons for aquatic biota and thus introduce more rigid time constraints on
122 maturation and reproduction, reduce population growth rates and increase the risk of
123 extinction (Tuytens et al. 2014, Pinceel et al. 2018). Aquatic-breeding amphibians are
124 also vulnerable to changes in wetland hydrology (Walls et al. 2013). Variation in
125 wetland hydroperiods due to precipitation extremes ~~has been shown to reduce~~ the
126 number of egg clutches and adult amphibians and affect the timing of amphibian
127 reproduction, which in turn may modify the composition of communities and interfere
128 with the ~~dynamics of~~ competitive and predatory interactions. The severity of the effects
129 will depend upon the individual species, its propensity for phenotypic plasticity and the
130 life history stage that is impacted.

131 ~~Considering this,~~ temporary wetlands are particularly sensitive to anthropogenic
132 pressures (Rhazi et al. 2001; Bouahim et al. 2014) and climate change (El Madihi et al.
133 2017; Pinceel et al. 2018). For instance, in Morocco, climate projections reveal that the
134 water deficit could increase by 16% to 67% in 2100 under the RCP8.5 scenario
135 (Representative Concentration Pathway 8.5 delivers a temperature increase of about
136 4.3°C by 2100) (Grillas et al. under review). The flooding duration ~~would~~ decrease

137 substantially and some wetlands will dry out completely (Grillas et al. **under review**).

138 Moreover, increased duration and intensity of drought are likely to favor the spread of

139 wildfires, which may ~~cause a transitory alteration of~~ faunal diversity patterns across

140 wetlands (Cunillera-Montcusi et al. **under review**).

141 The workshop participants further highlighted that climate change and water abstraction

142 may result in substantial water level fluctuations, with potentially major effects ~~even~~ on

143 the vegetation and associated organisms in the littoral zone of permanent water bodies,

144 especially ~~the~~ fish populations (Strayer and Findley 2010, Zohary and Ostrovsky 2011,

145 Cummings et al 2017).

146 **Likewise**, the reduction of the water volume in wetlands will ~~also~~ affect ~~the~~ water

147 quality (Zeng et al. 2013, Vega-Pozuelo 2018). Climate change can exacerbate

148 symptoms of eutrophication (Moss et al. 2011, Jeppesen et al. 2014) ~~as~~ prolonged

149 exposure to high nutrient loading has severe effects on wetland structure and

150 functioning (Sánchez-Carrillo et al. 2010, García-Muñoz et al. 2010, Gilbert et al.

151 2017). The increased temperature and frequency and duration of drought will also lead

152 to increased salinization affecting around $1/3$ of freshwater bodies (Jeppesen et al.

153 2020). Salinization effects have been poorly studied compared with other environmental

154 problems, but have gained increasing interest due to climate change (Waterkeyn et al.

155 2008, 2010b, 2011; Jeppesen et al. 2015, Cañedo-Argüelles et al. 2016, Vidal et al.

156 2021). **Enhanced** salinity has adverse effects on the fitness and survival of many aquatic

157 organisms and on ecosystem functioning and, consequently, on ecosystem services that

158 wetlands provide (Vidal et al. 2021).

159 Besides salinization, wetlands are also facing increased stress ~~by~~ other chemicals,

160 notably agrochemicals. The risk of pesticides pollution is greater in ~~those areas that may~~

161 ~~suffer~~ a water deficit under future scenarios (Tang et al. 2021). While some of the tools

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

162 and methodologies used in aquatic toxicology have been essential for developing water
163 quality guidelines (WQGs) by establishing legal maximum concentrations for many
164 pollutants (including salt) for different aquatic species (Nugegoda and Kibria 2013), it
165 ~~was emphasized at the workshop, that it~~ is time now to do more studies under more
166 realistic conditions, that account for ~~the complexity existing~~ at the ecosystem level
167 (Jeppesen et al. 2020). These ~~also~~ include multiple stressor effects (e.g. salinization,
168 eutrophication and chemical pollution) together with changing hydrology (Waterkeyn et
169 al. 2008, 2011; Arenas-Sánchez et al 2016). Although knowledge about the effects of
170 multiple stressors at the community and ecosystem level has increased recently (Segner
171 et al. 2014, Birk et al. 2020), we are still far from having achieved a general
172 understanding. It is necessary to move beyond the classical approaches, if we want to
173 identify direct and indirect effects of multiple stressors and develop relevant mitigation
174 methods (Rico et al. 2016). ~~Especially,~~ the interaction among pollutants and the direct
175 and indirect effects of climate change have been little studied in temporary wetlands and
176 ~~has~~ so far mainly focused on effects, but less on solutions (Parra and Ramos-Álvarez,
177 under review). The lack of ~~responses and~~ solutions is leading to the loss of wetland
178 integrity through pollution and water quality deterioration ~~unexpectedly~~ in protected
179 ecosystems. Two examples ~~of this~~ were presented at the workshop: (1) Doñana National
180 Park (southern Spain) where human activities have intensified over the last few decades,
181 affecting the water quality (and quantity) despite its environmental importance (Paredes
182 et al. 2019), and (2) the Fuente de Piedra wetland (southern Spain) that is affected by
183 wastewater discharge (De-los-Ríos-Mérida et al. 2017).
184 It is evident that mitigation of the effects of eutrophication, salinization and
185 agrochemical pollution are of key importance for preserving the water quality of
186 wetlands (Jackson et al. 2016, Cui et al. 2020) and new guidelines in environmental risk

187 assessment are needed (Geissen et al. 2015). Nature-based solutions (NBSs) may be a
188 way forward. As an example of NBS, De-los-Ríos-Mérida et al. (2021) found a slight
189 improvement in the quality of wastewater effluent passing through a stream with
190 artificial wetlands for natural purification before entering a Ramsar wetland (Fuente de
191 Piedra, southern Spain).

192 There are trade-offs, however, between protecting ecosystem integrity and guaranteeing
193 human welfare (social and economic components of sustainable development), which
194 need to be considered, and it is likely that a cocktail of approaches is needed when
195 weighing the environmental benefits of reducing the levels of contamination against the
196 economic, social and other environmental costs of the adopted action(s) (Van den Brink
197 et al. 2018). However, as wetlands do not have sufficient attention or recognition from
198 policy and decision makers, reinforcement of laws and regulations is crucial when
199 implementing restorative measures.

200

201 **The fate of egg and seed banks under climate change**

202 A major but often overlooked component of temporary wetlands is banks of eggs and
203 seeds in the wetland sediment, of specialised higher plant groups, zooplankton, large
204 branchiopods (Bonis et al. 1995, Brendonck and De Meester 2003, Olmo et al. 2020) as
205 well as other resting stages such as bacterial endospores, akinetes of cyanobacteria, and
206 cysts and spores of various protists (Souffreau et al. 2013). These banks of drought-
207 resistant propagules remain viable for an extended period of time in a state of dormancy
208 (resting stage with a strongly reduced metabolism). Only a few higher plant species are
209 restricted to the aquatic stage (hydrophytes); most are amphibious and survive, at least
210 for some weeks, after a wetland dries out. However, especially in dry summer climates,
211 only plant species having an annual life cycle with high seed production tolerate the

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

212 alternation between dry and flooded phases (Rhazi et al. 2001, Brock 2011). For
213 example, 70% of the plant species present in Mediterranean temporary wetlands are
214 annuals (Médail 2004).

215 While some aquatic invertebrates permanently inhabiting temporary wetlands produce
216 dormant propagules during the sexual phase of their life cycle (as most rotifers and
217 cladocerans do), other species are obligate sexual reproducers and produce resting eggs
218 in anticipation of deteriorating conditions (copepods) or during their entire lifespan
219 (large branchiopods) (Brendonck et al. 2017, Belmonte, 2020). Some ostracod species
220 have both sexual and asexual populations that also reveal diverse dormancy strategies
221 (Mesquita-Joanes et al. 2012).

222 The longevity of eggs and seeds in the soil of temporary wetlands affects egg and seed
223 bank richness and size (Bonis et al. 1995, Brock 2011, Olmo et al. 2020). Dormant eggs
224 of zooplankton and large branchiopods can survive for extended periods in the dry
225 sediment of temporary wetlands (Brendonck and De Meester, 2003), and also some
226 seeds may persist for prolonged periods when buried (Poschlod and Rosbakh, 2018).

227 When the inundation phase of temporary wetlands lasts long enough, egg loss due to
228 egg mortality and hatching from the egg bank will be compensated by the production of
229 new resting eggs that accumulate in the soil. To buffer for unsuccessful hatching, and
230 similar to the hatching strategies in desert annual plants, not all eggs will hatch at any
231 opportunity, but will do so when triggered by suitable conditions and with fractions that
232 theoretically reflect the local long-term chance for successful reproduction (bet-hedging
233 as part of a risk-spreading strategy) (Pinceel et al. 2017; Gremer and Venable 2014).

234 Under normal conditions, the above processes will, in the long term, result in a positive
235 egg and seed bank budget that can buffer against the typical natural intra- and inter-
236 seasonal climate variations of temporary wetlands. Ongoing and future climate change

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

237 may disturb these fine-tuned processes and not only impact on the structure and
238 functioning of the active, ~~but also of the dormant (egg bank)~~ components of the plant
239 and animal communities of temporary wetlands on which the demographic resilience
240 and persistence of populations depend (Pinceel et al. 2018). Making use of a population
241 matrix model, Pinceel et al. (2016a) underlined the importance of long-term survival of
242 resting eggs under a critical hydroperiod for persistence of local temporary rock pool
243 populations.
244 Due to ongoing and future climate change, shallow permanent wetlands may gradually
245 become semi-permanent or even dry out seasonally with accompanying changes in the
246 aquatic communities in the direction of more drought-adapted species that disperse
247 mainly by means of their dormant propagules. For example, a gradual historical climate
248 change with increasing aridification was the driver for diversification in Australian
249 *Branchinella* (Anostraca) species (Pinceel et al. 2013). However, the current speed of
250 climate change might be too fast for local populations to produce sufficient numbers of
251 eggs to replenish the egg bank (Tuýtens et al. 2014) or to adapt and accelerate growth
252 and maturation rates. Also, in plant communities, changes in the timing and duration of
253 flooding, as expected under climate change, will induce alterations in the composition
254 and abundance of species (Bliss and Zedler 1997, Grillas and Battedou 1998). Similar to
255 animals with egg banks, a reduced wetland hydroperiod will result in a diminished seed
256 bank density of plants and hence increased probability of population extinction (Faist
257 and Collinge 2015, Grillas et al. under review).
258 During the predicted prolonged periods of drought, egg banks will be exposed for an
259 extended duration to more frequent and more intense winds (Pinceel et al. 2020) that
260 will lead to impoverished egg banks (Brendonck and Riddoch 2000) and community
261 structure changes (Pinceel et al. 2016b). Most probably, the same mechanisms apply for

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

262 wetland vegetation and seedbanks with large inter-species differences in dispersal
263 propensity and rate, probably resulting from differences in seed size (Grillas et al
264 1993a).
265 Changing temperatures with more frequent and intensive heat waves will also directly
266 impact the dry egg bank, reducing egg hatching and survival (Brendonck et al. 1996,
267 Pinceel et al. 2018). Also plant seed germination will be affected, as most plant species
268 germinate at low temperatures as an adaptation to a winter-centred flood period,
269 although species differ in their optimum and breadth of the germination niche (Bonis et
270 al. 1995, Carta et al. 2013).
271 Dispersal of dormant eggs between wetlands can be affected by wind, overflows, water
272 birds and mammals, including humans (Green et al. 2002, Vanschoenwinkel et al. 2010,
273 Waterkeyn et al. 2010a, Lovas-Kiss et al. 2018) and involves interaction between the
274 communities of temporary wetland clusters (Lopes et al. 2016, Brendonck et al. 2017).
275 In such a metacommunity design, specific wetland patches can function as source, sink
276 or refuge. If some wetlands become uninhabitable due to climate change, the distance
277 for successful dispersal between wetlands may increase and impact wetland
278 metacommunity dynamics (Tuytens et al. 2014).
279 ~~As it has been mentioned in the previous section,~~ and being one of the major indirect
280 stressors induced by climate change (Waterkeyn et al. 2008, 2010b), increased salinity
281 has been shown to impact egg banks as well as active communities of large
282 branchiopods in Mediterranean temporary wetlands (Waterkeyn et al. 2011),
283 zooplankton composition (Antón-Pardo and Armegol 2012), cladoceran species
284 richness (Boronat et al. 2001), hatching rates of rotifers (García-Roger et al. 2008) and
285 other zooplankton groups (Valls et al. 2017). For some species, water conductivity acts
286 as a trigger for hatching (Vanschoenwinkel et al. 2010) but increased salinity at the time

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
287 of wetland filling may negatively impact the locally adapted hatching rate (Mabidi et al.
288 2018) and ultimately the persistence of the populations (Santangelo et al. 2014).
289 Similarly, whole plant community experiments in temporary coastal marshes showed
290 that salinity increase impacted the germination, growth and seed production
291 differentially for different plant species (Grillas et al. 1993b, Bonis et al. 1993).
292 As persistent egg and seed banks buffer the temporary wetland biota of drylands against
293 the often-high natural (intra and inter-seasonal) variability, it may be assumed that their
294 high resilience will also buffer against the effects of ongoing climate change. However,
295 the already known climate change impacts on egg and seed banks, as detailed above,
296 highlight their worsening status. Future research should therefore focus on the structure
297 and functioning of egg and seed banks in a multi-stressor environment with more
298 realistic scenarios with, for instance, mesocosm experiments ~~designs~~.

31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 55 56 57 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65 300 **The role of trophic web maintenance**

301 The aquatic communities of temporary wetlands are generally well adapted to climatic
302 variation since ~~the inhabiting~~ organisms have the ability to live underwater for months
303 and afterwards endure extreme conditions of drought during warm dry seasons (Sim et
304 al. 2013). However, extreme events, such as extended heat waves or very high or low
305 rainfall may, as already mentioned, induce stress to which existing adaptations of many
306 organisms are ineffective and cause profound shifts in aquatic invertebrate biodiversity
307 (Sim et al. 2013), plant species composition (Bagella and Caria 2013) and amphibian
308 communities (Wassens et al. 2013).
309 The changes in species composition and abundance of single organismal groups at a
310 particular trophic level induced by hydroperiod shifts may have cascading effects on the
311 species composition and abundance of other organism groups via links in the food web

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

312 (e.g. Pinero-Rodríguez et al. 2021). Different patterns between organisms having
313 different dispersion modes and abilities are expected as a consequence of shifts in the
314 hydroperiod of wetland (Sim et al. 2013, Kneitel 2016), leading to shifts in
315 communities. For example, for active dispersers, optimal dispersal conditions (i.e., late
316 spring) may become decoupled from the hydroperiod since they would occur when the
317 wetlands are dry (Boix et al. 2016).

318 However, the natural heterogeneity of biota in temporary wetlands and the often-rapid
319 ecological succession make it difficult to identify impacts of climate change on wetland
320 biota and food web (Jones et al. 2013). A long-term study of 30 small artificial wetlands
321 in Northumberland (UK) showed evidence of drought and inundation impacts on plants
322 and invertebrates (Jones et al. 2013, Jeffries et al. 2016). They suggested that shifts in
323 the length, intensity and frequency of the hydroperiod due to climate change will
324 degrade biota, including a decline in the abundance of characteristic temporary wetland
325 species whose adaptations may not be sufficient when faced with climate extremes
326 (Jeffries et al. 2016).

327 ~~As mentioned above, salinity affects the food web structure and therefore ecosystem~~
328 ~~functioning (Bruce et al. 2009, 2012, Jeppesen et al. 2015).~~ The structure of food webs
329 changes from high complexity in mesosaline lakes, having multiple trophic levels with
330 fish as top predators and diverse pelagic and littoral invertebrate assemblages (Hurlbert
331 et al. 1986, Hammer 1993), to ~~more~~ simplified food webs in hypersaline lakes with
332 amphipods as top predators and a shorter food web length (Lin et al. 2017, Golubkov et
333 al. 2018, Jeppesen et al. 2020, Shadrin and Anufrieva 2020). Studies using stable
334 isotope analysis suggest a declining food web complexity with increasing salinization
335 (Cooper and Wissel 2012). Vidal et al. (2021) studied the community and food web
336 structure in 24 lakes along a wide salinity gradient (i.e. subsaline to hypersaline lakes)

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

337 in a semiarid region in north-west China using a stable isotope approach. They found a
338 reduced number of taxa in all analysed communities and reduced complexity of the food
339 web with increasing salinity.

340 The shifts in trophic structure and food web complexity with increasing salinity are,
341 however, not simple, nor linear. For example, abrupt shifts can occur ~~when~~ specific
342 salinity thresholds ~~are reached~~ (Williams 1998, Brucet et al. 2009, 2010, Lin et al. 2017,
343 Jeppesen et al. 2020). Changes in size structure of fish have been observed as ~~a~~ negative
344 effect of increasing salinity (e.g. decrease in mean and maximum size; Sgarzi et al.
345 2020). When the salinity threshold for fish presence is ~~a~~ passed, large-bodied invertebrate
346 grazers ~~a~~ released from fish predation ~~a~~ become dominant. Another threshold is when the
347 salinity becomes too high for large-bodied cladocerans (e.g. *Daphnia*), provoking a shift
348 to dominance of anostraceans (*Artemia*). Although little information on the topic is
349 available, abrupt salinity shifts are dependent on the temperature and trophic state of ~~the~~
350 lakes as well as ~~by~~ seasonal variations in salinity.

351 There is, therefore, an urgent need for follow-up studies, for coming up with ~~wider-~~
352 ~~reaching~~ conclusions, allowing implementation of adequate management measures at
353 the watershed level (e.g. evidence based irrigation programmes) to prevent or mitigate
354 the expected induced future changes in food web structure and biodiversity (Vidal et al.,
355 2021).

356

357 **Temporary wetlands as hotspots of biodiversity**

358 Natural temporary wetlands are often hotspots of biodiversity due to their unique
359 environmental features. They are characterized by hosting a unique set of species; hence
360 in the Mediterranean region they are considered as priority habitats, to be conserved by
361 the EU's Habitats Directive (Zacharias and Zamparas 2010). Although these ecosystems

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

362 play a key role for the maintenance of regional biological diversity, information on
363 them is scarce or difficult to access. Studies carried out in Mediterranean temporary
364 wetlands have shown high species richness (Waterkeyn et al. 2008, Rhazi et al. 2012,
365 Gilbert et al. 2015, Blanco et al. 2020, Cunillera-Montcusí et al. under review), with the
366 occurrence of endemic or rare species at regional scales (Blanco et al. 2019a, b,
367 Marrone et al. 2020, Yılmaz et al. 2020). Moreover, these ecosystems also show high
368 singularity (sensu Boix et al. 2008) and uniqueness values, which, together with the
369 high species richness, make them biodiversity hotspots.
370 Another relevant feature is connectivity, a key concept in species richness maintenance.
371 High diatom diversity was reported in spatially grouped mountain wetlands (Blanco et
372 al. 2020) supporting the hypothesis that species assemblages tend to be richer in areas
373 that facilitate propagule dispersal and colonization, such as connected temporary
374 wetlands (see also the section on egg and seed banks).
375 The typical inherent intra- and inter-annual fluctuations in the limnological features of
376 wetlands drastically affect the seasonal variation in the structure and dynamics of the
377 aquatic community, leading to increased heterogeneity and subsequently the
378 biodiversity. As indicated in previous sections, studies have shown that the hydroperiod,
379 time of flooding-desiccation, salinity, and trophic state are the main drivers determining
380 species richness and community composition of plants and animals in Mediterranean
381 wetlands (Alonso 1998, López-González et al. 1998, Brucet et al. 2009; Gilbert et al
382 under review).
383 Regions of permanent waterbodies, river floodplains and eulittoral lake zones (i.e. the
384 region between the maximum and minimum waterlines), that are wet only part of the
385 time and are acting transiently as temporary wetlands, are gaining attention in
386 biodiversity studies. In lakes with substantial water level fluctuations, the eulittoral zone

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

387 tends to become overgrown by shore vegetation when dry. Then, with rising water
388 levels, the vegetation is inundated and inhabited by macrophytes, invertebrates, fish and
389 birds (Cummings et al. 2017). As the amplitude of water level fluctuations increases on
390 a multi-annual scale, the stress on the aquatic biota inhabiting the eulittoral zone
391 increases, converting it into a “desert” under extreme fluctuations, as is typical for
392 reservoirs used for hydropower generation. The belt of water level fluctuations around
393 lakes is understudied ~~for most large lakes~~. Given current global warming, it warrants
394 much greater scientific interest.

395 Besides, the Intergovernmental Panel for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES
396 2018) listed invasive species as one of the five main drivers of biodiversity loss leading
397 to transformation of natural ecosystems (Yilmaz et al. 2021). The importance of
398 exotic/invasive species in shaping the ecological characteristics of temporary wetlands,
399 including impacts from introduced domestic animals, such as cattle and goats, requires
400 special attention, as wetlands often ~~are~~ hotspots for endemic species.

401

402 Resilience

403 Resilience is a critical property of ecosystems ~~that let to~~ return to their original state
404 after disturbance or to absorb disturbances **before shifting to another state, while**
405 **remaining within the stable states** (e.g. Holling 2001, IPCC 2014). Critical shifts
406 between contrasting states in aquatic systems may be a consequence of persistent and
407 small fluctuations (Scheffer et al. 2012). For instance, the severity and intensity of a
408 drought can induce a transient state known as the "ghost state", where a clear and
409 unstable state is maintained most of the time despite ~~the~~ high concentrations of nutrients
410 (van Geest et al. 2007). On the other hand, regime shifts may lead to a strong
411 degradation and eventually to an alternative stable state (Walker et al. 2004). This

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

412 process occurs when ecosystems do not have sufficient ecological resilience to absorb
413 disturbances and hence ~~to~~ remain within a given stable state (e.g. Peterson et al. 1998).
414 According to IPCC (2014) the conditions that wetland biota ~~is~~ adapted to, will ~~suffer~~
415 ~~alterations~~, which may lead to a loss of resilience (Baho et al. 2017).
416 There is growing awareness among ecologists and managers of the need to assess
417 resilience with different hypothesis frameworks ~~proposed (i.e the slow recovery;~~ Van de
418 Leemput et al. 2018) and increasing ~~the amount of~~ studies on the effects of landscape
419 spatial features on resilience (Allen et al. 2016). ~~Among the main aspects approached~~
420 ~~are~~ spatial regime description, disturbance intensity, ecological memory and functional
421 connectivity (Allen et al. 2016). As a result, the concept of resilience has changed over
422 time and currently incorporates multidisciplinary perspectives.
423 Studies on functional traits and adaptive strategies have been widely used to predict the
424 future state of temporary waters (Bazzanti et al. 2009, Schmera et al. 2017). Here,
425 environmental filters determine the selection of traits and strategies, which in turn
426 influence the process and functioning of aquatic ecosystems. Currently, the enhanced
427 magnitude of drought has changed the water regime of temporary wetlands, acting as a
428 powerful filter and increasing the abundance of the most tolerant species in adverse
429 conditions, such as salt-tolerant species (Castillo et al. 2018, Vidal et al. 2021). For
430 example, results from macroinvertebrate studies have shown high sensitivity of
431 gatherers and filterers to salinity (Castillo et al. 2018). For the most part, recovery is
432 rapid and favoured by species characteristics, indicating high resilience of aquatic
433 communities to disturbances (Fritz and Dodds 2004). To face the typical disturbance
434 regimen in temporary wetlands, the main characteristics of the species reported were
435 widespread dispersal, high abundances and high growth rates ~~are among the most~~
436 ~~important~~ (Williams 2006). The evolutionary process selects traits and strategies that

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

437 are adapted to seasonal drying and flooding over time, but the speed of current changes,
438 can limit this adaptive capacity.

439 A timely and urgent goal for wetland scientists is to understand the main mechanisms
440 associated with ~~the~~ disturbance by extreme drought ~~and~~ reduced resilience and ~~how this~~
441 ~~affects~~ aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem functioning in ~~unpredictable~~ scenarios. To
442 reconcile the concept of ecological resilience with natural disturbances and human
443 impacts (Angeler 2021) ~~in order to~~ establish more efficient management strategies ~~is~~
444 ~~also an urgent research need. The connections among the thematic blocks placed on the~~
445 ~~table in the workshop, typical of complex systems, should move us to search onto~~
446 ~~emergent behaviours and properties~~ in order to anticipate future scenarios and reach
447 solutions. Research networks operating at different levels (from local to international
448 level) and the collaboration with all the stakeholders would promote the sharing of
449 knowledge and ~~the solving problems actions to~~ enhance protection of these endangered
450 aquatic systems.

451

452 **Post COVID-19 challenges**

453 During the workshop it became evident that the SARS-CoV-2 was spreading
454 developing into a pandemic. The effects on human health, but also on the world
455 economy will undoubtedly slow the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals
456 (SDGs), probably entailing a need for further prioritisation of specific goals within
457 individual countries or regions (Naidoo and Fisher 2020). This is reasonable and
458 manageable, but actions in response to the environmental crisis cannot be delayed, as
459 shown by the urgency of the situation for wetlands globally, as recently outlined in the
460 Second Warning to Humanity (Finlayson et al. 2019) and Global Wetland Outlook
461 (Ramsar Convention on Wetlands 2018). The measures introduced to control the

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

462 pandemic, and their consequences and impact on aquatic ecosystems, are a topic that
463 needs immediate attention (El-Nahhal and El-Nahhal 2020). The gap between the
464 identification of the need for emergency actions and the time needed for the necessary
465 decisions to be made and subsequent actions taken is a further threat to wetlands.
466 Hence the importance of this **special issue** as a step towards leveraging greater efforts to
467 ensure their protection based on scientific evidence.

468 Acknowledgements

469 We thank Andalusian International University for funding the workshop and the Centre
470 for Advanced Studies in Earth Sciences (UJA) the grants for students attending. SB was
471 supported by the PONDERFUL project (Pond ecosystems for resilient future landscapes
472 in a changing climate) funded by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
473 innovation programme under grant agreement No 869296. EJ was supported by the
474 TÜBİTAK researchers program BİDEB 2232 (project 118C250). TZ was supported by
475 the Israel Water Authority.
476

477 478 479 REFERENCES.

480 Allen CR, Angeler DG, Cumming GS, Folke C, Twidwell D, Uden DR. 2016.
481 Quantifying spatial resilience. *J Appl Ecol.* 53 (3):625–635
482 Alonso M. 1998. Las lagunas de la España Penínsular. *Limnetica.* 15:1-176.
483 **Angeler DG. 2021. Conceptualizing resilience in temporary waters. *Inland Waters.* (this**
484 **issue).**

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 485 Antón-Pardo M, Armengol X. 2012. Effects of salinity and water temporality on
486 zooplankton community in coastal Mediterranean ponds. *Estuar Coast Shelf*
487 *Sci.* 114:93–99.
- 488 Arenas-Sánchez A, Rico A, Vighi M. 2016. Effects of water scarcity and chemical
489 pollution in aquatic ecosystems: State of the art. *Sci Total Environ.* 572:390-
490 403.
- 491 Bagella S, Caria MC. 2013. Sensitivity of ephemeral wetland swards with *Isoetes*
492 *histrix* Bory to environmental variables: implications for the conservation of
493 Mediterranean temporary ponds. *Aquat Conserv Mar Freshw Ecos.* 23:277–
494 290.
- 495 Baho DL, Allen CR, Garmestani A, Fried-Petersen H, Renes SE, Gunderson L, Angeler
496 DG. 2017. A quantitative framework for assessing ecological resilience. *Ecol*
497 *Soc.* 22(3): art17.
- 498 Bazzanti M, Bella VD, Grezzi F. 2009. Functional characteristics of macroinvertebrate
499 communities in Mediterranean ponds (Central Italy): influence of water
500 permanence and mesohabitat type. *Ann Limnol.* 45:29–39.
- 501 Belmonte G. 2020. The suspected contradictory role of parental care in the adaptation of
502 planktonic calanoida to temporary freshwater. *Water.* 2021, 13, 100.
- 503 Blanco S, Olenici A, Ortega F, Jiménez-Gómez F, Guerrero F. 2019a. Taxonomía y
504 morfología de *Craticula gadorensis* sp. nov. (Bacillariophyta,
505 Stauroneidaceae). *Bol Soc Argent Bot.* 54:5-11.
- 506 Blanco S, Olenici A, Jiménez-Gómez F, Ortega F, Guerrero F. 2019b. Una nueva
507 especie del género *Hantzchia* (Bacillariaceae) en Almería, España. *Caldasia.*
508 41:343-348.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 509 Blanco S, Olenici A, Ortega F, Jiménez-Gómez F, Guerrero F. 2020. Identifying
510 environmental drivers of benthic diatom diversity: the case of Mediterranean
511 mountain ponds. *PeerJ*. 8:e8825.
- 512 Bliss S, Zedler P. 1997. The germination process in vernal pools: Sensitivity to
513 environmental conditions and effects on community structure. *Oecologia*.
514 113:67–73.
- 515 Birk S, Chapman D, Carvalho L, Spears BM, Andersen HE, Argillier C, ... Bondar-
516 Kunze E. 2020. Impacts of multiple stressors on freshwater biota across spatial
517 scales and ecosystems. *Nat Ecol Evol*. 4(8):1060-1068.
- 518 Bouahim S, Rhazi L, Amami B, Waterkeyn A Rhazi M, Saber E-R, Zouahri A, Van den
519 Broeck M, Muller SD, Brendonck L., Grillas P. 2014. Unraveling the impact of
520 anthropogenic pressure on plant communities in Mediterranean temporary
521 ponds. *Mar Freshwater Res*. 65:918–929.
- 522 Bonis A, Grillas P, Wijck C van, Lepart J. 1993. The effect of salinity on the
523 reproduction of coastal submerged macrophytes in experimental communities.
524 *J Veg Sci*. 4(4):461–468.
- 525 Bonis A, Lepart J, Grillas P. 1995. Seed Bank Dynamics and Coexistence of Annual
526 Macrophytes in a Temporary and Variable Habitat. *Oikos*. 74(1):81.
- 527 Boix D, Gascón S, Sala J, Badosa A, Brucet S, López-Flores R, Martinoy M, Gifre J,
528 Quintana XD. 2008. Patterns of composition and species richness of
529 crustaceans and aquatic insects along environmental gradients in
530 Mediterranean water bodies. *Hydrobiologia*. 597:53-69.
- 531 Boix D, Kneitel J, Robson J, Duchet BJ, Zúñiga C, Day L, Gascón J, Sala J, Quintana
532 XD, Blaustein L. 2016. Invertebrates of Freshwater Temporary Ponds in

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

533 Mediterranean Climates. In: Batzer D, Boix D. (eds) Invertebrates in
534 Freshwater Wetlands. Springer, Cham.
535 Boronat L, Miracle MR, Armengol X. 2001. Cladoceran assemblages in a
536 mineralization gradient. *Hydrobiologia*. 442:75-88.
537 Bracewell S, Verdonshot RC, Schäfer RB, Bush A, Lapen DR, Van den Brink PJ.
538 2019. Qualifying the effects of single and multiple stressors on the food web
539 structure of Dutch drainage ditches using a literature review and conceptual
540 models. *Sci Total Environ*. 684:727-740.
541
542 Brendonck L. 1996. Diapause, quiescence, hatching requirements: what we can learn
543 from large freshwater branchiopods (Crustacea: Branchiopoda: Anostraca,
544 Notostraca, Conchostraca). *Hydrobiologia*. 320:85-97.
545 Brendonck L, Riddoch BJ. 2000. Egg bank dynamics in anostracan desert rock pool
546 populations (Crustacea: Branchiopoda). *Archiv Hydrobiol*. 148:71-84.
547 Brendonck L, De Meester L. 2003. Egg banks in freshwater zooplankton: Evolutionary
548 and ecological archives in the sediment. *Hydrobiologia*. 491:65-84.
549 Brendonck L, Jocqué M, Tuytens K, Timms BV, Vanschoenwinkel B. 2015.
550 Hydrological stability drives both local and regional diversity patterns in rock
551 pool metacommunities. *Oikos*. 124(6): 741-749.
552 Brendonck L, Pinceel T, Ortells R. 2017. Dormancy and dispersal as mediators of
553 zooplankton population and community dynamics along a hydrological
554 disturbance gradient in inland temporary pools. *Hydrobiologia*. 796:201–222.
555 Brock MA. 2011. Persistence of seed banks in Australian temporary wetlands. *Freshw*
556 *Biol*. 56(7):1312–1327.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 557 Brucet S, Boix D, Gascón S, Sala J, Quintana XD, Badosa A, Søndergaard M,
558 Lauridsen TL, Jeppesen E. 2009. Species richness of crustacean zooplankton
559 and trophic structure of brackish lagoons in contrasting climate zones: north
560 temperate Denmark and Mediterranean Catalonia (Spain). *Ecography*. 32:692-
561 702.
- 562 Brucet S, Boix D, Nathansen LW, Quintana XD, Jensen E, Balayla D, Meerhoff M,
563 Jeppesen E. 2012. Effects of temperature, salinity and fish in structuring the
564 macroinvertebrate community in shallow lakes: Implications for effects of
565 climate change. *PLoS ONE* 7(2): e30877
- 566 Cañedo-Argüelles M, Hawkins CP, Kefford BJ, Schäfer RB, Dyack BJ, Brucet S,
567 Buchwalter D, Dunlop J, Frör O, Lazorchak J, Coring E, Fernandez HR,
568 Goodfellow W, González Achem AL, Hatfield-Dodds S, Karimov BK, Mensah
569 P, Olson JR, Piscart C, Prat N, Ponsá S, Schulz CJ, Timpano AJ. 2016. Saving
570 freshwater from salts. *Science*. 351, 914-916
- 571 Carta A, Bedini G, Müller JV, Probert RJ. 2013. Comparative seed dormancy and
572 germination of eight annual species of ephemeral wetland vegetation in a
573 Mediterranean climate. *Plant Ecol*. 214(2):339–349.
- 574 Castillo AM, Sharpe DMT, Ghalambor CK, De León LF. 2018. Exploring the effects of
575 salinization on trophic diversity in freshwater ecosystems: A quantitative
576 review. *Hydrobiologia*. 807:1081– 1097.
- 577 Chen L, Li S, Zhou Y, Zhou X, Jiang H, Liu X, Yuan S. 2020. Risk assessment for
578 pesticide mixtures on aquatic ecosystems in China: a proposed framework. *Pest*
579 *Manag Sci*. 76(2):444-453.
- 580 Cooper RN, Wissel B. 2012. Loss of trophic complexity in saline prairie lakes as
581 indicated by stable-isotope based community-metrics. *Aquat Biosyst*. 8:6.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 582 Cui S, Yu T, Zhang F, Fu Q, Hough R, An L, ... Pei Z. 2020. Understanding the risks
583 from diffuse pollution on wetland eco-systems: The effectiveness of water
584 quality classification schemes. *Ecol Eng.* 155:105929.
- 585 Cummings D, Goren M, Gasith A, Zohary T. 2017. Inundated shore vegetation as
586 habitat for cichlids breeding in a lake subjected to extreme water level
587 fluctuations. *Inland Waters.* 7(4), 449-460.
- 588 Cunillera-Montcusí D, Boix D, Tornero I, Quintana XD, Sala J, Gascon S. 2021 .
589 Changes in diversity of Mediterranean temporary ponds faunal communities
590 after the impact of a wildfire. *Inland Waters.* (under review).
- 591 De-los-Ríos-Mérida J, Reul A, Muñoz M, Arijo-Andrade S, Tapia-Paniagua S, Rendón-
592 Martos M, Guerrero F. 2017. How efficient are the semi-natural ponds on the
593 assimilation of wastewater effluents? The case of a Mediterranean Ramsar
594 wetland (Fuente de Piedra, south of Spain). *Water.* 2017, 9, 600.
- 595 De-los-Ríos-Mérida J, Guerrero F, Arijo S, Muñoz M, Álvarez-Manzaneda I, García-
596 Márquez J, Rendón-Martos M, Bautista B, & Reul, A. (2021). Wastewater
597 Discharge through a Stream into a Mediterranean Ramsar Wetland: Evaluation
598 and Proposal of a Nature-Based Treatment System. *Sustainability.* 2021, 13,
599 3540.
- 600 Döll P., Zhang J. 2010. Impact of climate change on freshwater ecosystems: a global-
601 scale analysis of ecologically relevant river flow alterations. *Hydrol Earth Syst*
602 *Sci.* 14:783–799.
- 603 El Madihi M, Rhazi L, Van den Broeck M, Rhazi M, Waterkeyn A, Saber E., Arahou
604 M, Zouhari A, Muller SD, Brendonck L, Grillas P. 2017. Plant community
605 patterns in Moroccan temporary ponds along latitudinal and anthropogenic
606 disturbance gradients. *Plant Ecol Divers.* 10:197–215.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 607 El-Nahhal I, El-Nahhal Y. 2020. Ecological consequences of COVID-19 outbreak. J
608 Water Sci Eng. 1:1-5.
- 609 Faist AM, Collinge SK. 2015. Seed bank composition varies along invasion and
610 inundation gradients in vernal pool wetlands. *Plant Ecol.* 216(4):553–564.
- 611 Finlayson CM, Davies GT, Moomaw WR, Chmura GL, Natali SM, Perry JE, Roulet N,
612 Sutton-Grier AE. 2018. The Second Warning to Humanity – providing a
613 context for wetland management and policy. *Wetlands.* 39:1-5.
- 614 Fritz KM, Dodds WK. 2004. Resistance and resilience of macroinvertebrate
615 assemblages to drying and flood in a tallgrass prairiestream system.
616 *Hydrobiologia.* 527:99-112
- 617 García-Muñoz E, Gilbert JD, Parra G, Guerrero F. 2010. Wetlands classification for
618 amphibian conservation in Mediterranean landscapes. *Biodivers Conserv.*
619 19(3): 901-911.
- 620 García-Roger, EM, Armengol-Díaz X, Carmona MJ, Serra M. 2008. Assessing rotifer
621 diapausing egg bank diversity and abundance in brackish temporary
622 environments: an ex situ sediment incubation approach. *Arch Hydrobiol.*
623 173(1):79-88.
- 624 Geissen V, Mol H, Klumpp E, Umlauf G, Nadal M, van der Ploeg M, van de Zee S,
625 Ritsema CJ. 2015. Emerging pollutants in the environment: a challenge for
626 water resource management. *Int Soil Water Conserv Res.* 3(1):57-65.
- 627 Gilbert JD, de Vicente I, Ortega F, Jiménez-Melero R, Parra G, Guerrero F. 2015. A
628 comprehensive evaluation of the crustacean assemblages in southern Iberian
629 Mediterranean wetlands. *J Limnol.* 74:169-181.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 630 Gilbert JD, de Vicente I, Ortega F, García-Muñoz E, Jiménez-Melero R, Parra G,
631 Guerrero F. 2017. Linking watershed land uses and crustacean assemblages in
632 Mediterranean wetlands. *Hydrobiologia*. 799:181-191.
- 633 Gilbert, J.D.; I. de Vicente; F. Ortega; F. Guerrero (under review). Zooplankton
634 community dynamic in temporary Mediterranean wetlands: which drivers are
635 controlling the seasonal species replacement? *Water*
- 636 Golubkov SM, Shadrin NV, Golubkov MS, Balushkina EV, Litvinchuk LF. 2018. Food
637 chains and their dynamics in ecosystems of shallow lakes with different water
638 salinities. *Rus J Ecol*. 49: 442-448.
- 639 Gremer JR, Venable DL. 2014. Bet hedging in desert winter annual plants: optimal
640 germination strategies in a variable environment. *Ecol Lett.* 17(3):380–387.
- 641 Green AJ, Figuerola J, Sánchez MI. 2002. Implications of waterbird ecology for the
642 dispersal of aquatic organisms. *Acta Oecologica*. 23(3):177–189.
- 643 Grillas P, Garcia-Murillo P, Geertz-Hansen O, Marba N, Montes C, Duarte CM, Tan
644 Ham L, Grossmann A. 1993a. Submerged macrophyte seed bank in a
645 Mediterranean temporary marsh: Abundance and relationship with established
646 vegetation. *Oecologia*. 94 p1-6.
- 647 Grillas P, Wijck C van, Bonis A. 1993b. The effect of salinity on the dominance-
648 diversity relations of experimental coastal macrophyte communities. *J Veg Sci*.
649 4(4):453–460.
- 650 Grillas P, Battedou G. 1998. Effects of the date of flooding on the biomass, species
651 composition and seed production of submerged macrophyte beds in temporary
652 marshes in the Camargue (S. France). Proceedings of the Intecol Conference,
653 Perth, September 1996. In: Wetlands for the Future (McComb AJ, Davis JA.
654 eds), INTECOL'S V International Wetland Conference, pp: 207-218.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 655 Grillas P, Rhazi L, Lefebvre G, El Madihi M, Poulin B. 2021. Foreseen impact of
656 climate change on temporary ponds located along a latitudinal gradient in
657 Morocco. *Inland Waters*. (this issue).
- 658 Hammer UT. 1993. Zooplankton distribution and abundance in saline lakes of Alberta
659 and Saskatchewan, Canada. *Int J Salt Lake Res*. 2:111-132.
- 660 Holling, C.S. 2001. Understanding the complexity of economic, ecological, and social
661 systems. *Ecosystems*. 4(5):390-405.
- 662 Hurlbert SH, Loayza W, Moreno T. 1986. Fish-flamingo-plankton interactions in the
663 Peruvian Andes. *Limnol Oceanogr*. 31:457-468.
- 664 IPBES. 2018. The IPBES regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem
665 services for Europe and Central Asia. Rounsevell M, Fischer M, Torre-Marín
666 Rando A and Mader A (eds.). Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-
667 Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem services, Bonn, Germany
- 668 IPCC. 2014. Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups
669 I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on
670 Climate Change [Core Writing Team, R.K. Pachauri and L.A. Meyer (eds.)].
671 IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland, 151 pp.
- 672 Jackson MC, Loewen CJ, Vinebrooke RD, Chimimba CT. 2016. Net effects of multiple
673 stressors in freshwater ecosystems: a meta-analysis. *Global Change Biol*.
674 22(1):180-189.
- 675 Jeffries MJ, Epele LB, Studinski JM, Vad CF. 2016. Invertebrates in Temporary
676 Wetland Ponds of the Temperate Biomes. In: Batzer D., Boix D. (eds)
677 Invertebrates in Freshwater Wetlands. Springer, Cham.
- 678 Jeppesen E, Meerhoff M, Davidson TA, Trolle D, Søndergaard M, Lauridsen TL,
679 Beklioglu M, Brucet S, Volta P, González-Bergonzoni I, Nielsen A. 2014.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

680 Climate change impacts on lakes: an integrated ecological perspective based on
681 a multi-faceted approach, with special focus on shallow lakes. *J Limnol.*
682 73(s1):84-107.

683 Jeppesen E, Brucet S, Naselli-Flores L, Papastergiadou E, Stefanidis K, Nöges T, Nöges
684 P, Attayde JL, Zohary T, Coppens J, et al. 2015. Ecological impacts of global
685 warming and water abstraction on lakes and reservoirs due to changes in water
686 level and related changes in salinity. *Hydrobiologia.* 750:201-227.

687 Jeppesen E, Beklioglu M, Özkan K, Akyurek Z. 2020. Salinization increase due to
688 climate change will have substantial negative effects on inland waters and
689 freshwater resources: A call for multifaceted research at the local and global
690 scale. *The Innovation.* 1:100030.

691 Jones I, Abrahams C, Brown L, Dale K, Edwards F, Jeffries M, ... Murphy J. 2013. The
692 impact of extreme events on freshwater ecosystems. *Brit Ecol Soc, London* pp
693 37.

694 Keddy PA. 2000. *Wetland Ecology: Principles and Conservation.* Cambridge University
695 Press.

696 Kneitel J. 2016. Climate-driven habitat size determines the latitudinal diversity gradient
697 in temporary ponds. *Ecology.* 97:961–968.

698 Lin Q, Xu L, Liu Z, Jeppesen E, Han BP. 2017. Responses of trophic structure and
699 zooplankton community to salinity and temperature in Tibetan Lakes:
700 Implication for the effect of climate. *Wat Res.* 124:618–629.

701 Lopes PM, Bozelli R, Bini LM, Santangelo JM, Declerck SAJ. 2016. Contributions of
702 airborne dispersal and dormant propagule recruitment to the assembly of rotifer
703 and crustacean zooplankton communities in temporary ponds. *Freshw Biol.*
704 61(5):658-669.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 705 López-González P, Guerrero F, Castro MC. 1998. Seasonal fluctuations in the plankton
706 community in a hypersaline temporary lake (Honda, southern Spain). *Int. J.*
707 *Salt Lake Res.* 6: 353-371.
- 708 Lovas-Kiss A, Sánchez M I, Molnár A, Valls L, Armengol X, Mesquita-Joanes F,
709 Green A. J. 2018. Crayfish invasion facilitates dispersal of plants and
710 invertebrates by gulls. *Freshw Biol.* 63:392 – 404.
- 711 Mabidi A, Bird M S, Perissinotto R. 2018. Increasing salinity drastically reduces
712 hatching success of crustaceans from depression wetlands of the semi-arid
713 Eastern Cape Karoo region, South Africa. *Sci Rep.* 8:1-9.
- 714 Marrone F, Ortega F, Mesquita-Joanes F, Guerrero F. 2020. On the occurrence of
715 *Metadiaptomus chevreuxi* (Calanoida, Diaptomidae, Paradiaptominae) in the
716 Iberian Peninsula, with notes on the ecology and distribution of its European
717 populations. *Water.* 2020, 12, 1989.
- 718 MEA 2005. Ecosystems and human well-being: wetlands and water synthesis. World
719 Resources Institute, Washington, DC.
720 <http://www.millenniumassessment.org/documents/document.358.aspx.pdf>
- 721 Médail F. 2004. Plant species. In: Grillas P et alii, editor. Mediterranean temporary
722 pools 1: Issues relating to conservation, functioning and management. Arles:
723 Tour du Valat; p. 118.
- 724 Mesquita-Joanes F, Smith A, Viehberg F. 2012. The ecology of Ostracoda across levels
725 of biological organisation from individual to ecosystem: a review of recent
726 developments and future potential. In: Horne, D.J., Holmes, J.A., Rodríguez-
727 Lázaro J, Viehberg F. (Eds.). *Ostracoda as proxies for Quaternary climate*
728 *change. Developments in Quaternary Science Series, 17: 15-35. Elsevier,*
729 *Amsterdam*

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

730 Moss B, Kosten S, Meerhoff M, Battarbee RW, Jeppesen E, Mazzeo N, ... Paerl H.
731 2011. Allied attack: climate change and eutrophication. *Inland Waters*. 1(2):
732 101-105.

733 Naidoo R, Fisher B. 2020. Reset Sustainable Development Goals for a pandemic world.
734 *Nature*, 583.

735 Nugegoda D, Kibria G. 2013. Water quality guidelines for the protection of aquatic
736 ecosystems. In: *Encyclopedia of Aquatic Ecotoxicology*, DOI, 10. pp. 978–94.

737 Olmo C, Antón-Pardo M, Ortells R, Armengol X. 2020. Influence of restoration age on
738 egg bank richness and composition: an ex situ experiment. *J Plankton Res.*
739 42(5):553–563.

740 Paredes I, Ramírez F, Forero MG, Green AJ. 2019. Stable isotopes in helophytes
741 reflect anthropogenic nitrogen pollution in entry streams at the Doñana World
742 Heritage Site. *Ecol Indic.* 97:130-140.

743 Parra G, Ramos-Álvarez MM. 2021. Climate and chemical stressors in temporary
744 wetlands: A review of progress and the way forward. *Inland Waters*. (under
745 review).

746 Peterson G, Allen CR, Holling CS. 1998. Ecological resilience, biodiversity, and scale.
747 *Ecosystems*. 1:6–18.

748 Phillips JC, McKinley GA, Bennington V, Bootsma HA, Pilcher DJ, Sterner RW,
749 Urban NR. 2015. The Potential for CO₂-Induced Acidification in Freshwater:
750 A Great Lakes Case Study. *Oceanography* 25(2):136–145.
751 doi:10.5670/oceanog.2015.37.

752 Pinceel T, Brendonck L, Larmuseau MHD, Vanhove MPM, Timms BV,
753 Vanschoenwinkel B. 2013. Environmental change as a driver of diversification

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 754 in temporary aquatic habitats: Does the genetic structure of extant fairy shrimp
755 populations reflect historic aridification? *Freshw Biol.* 58(8):1556-1572.
- 756 Pinceel T, Vanschoenwinkel B, Brendonck L, Buschke F. 2016a. Modelling the
757 sensitivity of life history traits to climate change in a temporary pool
758 crustacean. *Sci Rep.* 6, 29451.
- 759 Pinceel T, Brendonck L, Vanschoenwinkel B. 2016b. Propagule size and shape may
760 promote local wind dispersal in freshwater zooplankton-a wind tunnel
761 experiment. *Limnol Oceanog.* 61(1), 122-131.
- 762 Pinceel TB, Vanschoenwinkel W, Hawinkel, Tuytens K, Brendonck L. 2017. Aridity
763 promotes bet hedging via delayed hatching: a case study with two temporary
764 pond crustaceans along a latitudinal gradient. *Oecologia* 184:161-170.
- 765 Pinceel T, Buschke F, Weckx M, Brendonck L, Vanschoenwinkel B. 2018. Climate
766 change jeopardizes the persistence of freshwater zooplankton by reducing both
767 habitat suitability and demographic resilience. *BMC Ecol.* 18(1):1-9.
- 768 Pinceel T, Vanschoenwinkel B, Weckx M, Brendonck L. 2020. An empirical test of the
769 impact of drying events and physical disturbance on wind erosion of
770 zooplankton egg banks in temporary ponds. *Aquat Ecol.* 54(1):137-144.
- 771 **Pinero-Rodríguez M, Gómez-Mestre I, Díaz-Paniagua C. 2021. Herbivory by spadefoot**
772 **toad tadpoles and reduced water level affect the abundance and life-history of**
773 **submerged plants in temporary ponds. *Inland Waters* (this issue).**
- 774 Poschlod P, Rosbakh S. 2018. Mudflat species: Threatened or hidden? An extensive
775 seed bank survey of 108 fish ponds in Southern Germany. *Biol Conserv.*
776 225:154–163.
- 777 Ramsar 2002. COP8 Resolution VIII.33 Guidance for identifying, sustainably
778 managing, and designating temporary pools as Wetlands of International

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

779 Importance. 8th Meeting of the Conference of the Contracting Parties to the
780 Convention on Wetlands. Pp 6.
781 Ramsar Convention on Wetlands. 2018. Global Wetland Outlook: State of the World's
782 Wetlands and their Services to People. Gland, Switzerland: Ramsar
783 Convention Secretariat.
784 Rhazi L, Grillas P, Mounirou Toure A, Tan Ham L. 2001. Impact of land use in
785 catchment and human activities on water, sediment and vegetation of
786 Mediterranean temporary pools. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences*
787 - Series III - Sciences de la Vie. 324(2):165–177.
788 Rhazi L, Grillas P, Saber ER, Rhazi M, Brendonck L, Waterkeyn A. 2012. Vegetation
789 of Mediterranean temporary pools: a fading jewel? *Hydrobiologia* 19: 85-95.
790 Rico A, Van den Brink PJ, Gylstra R, Focks A, Brock TC. 2016. Developing ecological
791 scenarios for the prospective aquatic risk assessment of pesticides. *Integr*
792 *Environ Assess Manag.* 12(3):510-521.
793 Rosset V. Lehmann A. Oertli B. 2010. Warmer and richer? Predicting the impact of
794 climate warming on species richness in small temperate water bodies. *Global*
795 *Change Biol.* 16:2376–2387.
796 Sánchez-Carrillo S, Angeler DG, Álvarez-Cobelas M, Sánchez-Andrés R. 2010.
797 Freshwater wetland eutrophication. In: *Eutrophication: causes, consequences*
798 *and control.* Springer; pp. 195-210.
799 Santangelo JM, Esteves FDA, Manca M, Bozelli RL. 2014. Disturbances due to
800 increased salinity and the resilience of zooplankton communities: The potential
801 role of the resting egg bank. *Hydrobiologia.* 722(1):103-113.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 802 Scheffer M, Carpenter SR, Lenton TM, Bascompte J, Brock W, Dakos V, van de
803 Koppel J, van de Leemput IA, Levin SA, van Nes EH, Pascual M, Vandermeer
804 J. 2012. Anticipating critical transitions. *Science*. 338:344–8.
- 805 Schmera D, Heino J, Podani J, Erős T, Dolédec S. 2017. Functional diversity: a review
806 of methodology and current knowledge in freshwater macroinvertebrate
807 research. *Hydrobiologia*. 787(1):27–44
- 808 Segner H, Schmitt-Jansen M, Sabater S. 2014. Assessing the impact of multiple
809 stressors on aquatic biota: The receptor’s side matters. *Environ Sci Technol*.
810 48:7690–7696.
- 811 Sgarzi S, Brucet S, Bartrons M, Arranz I, Benejam L, Badosa A. 2020. Factors
812 Influencing Abundances and Population Size Structure of the Threatened and
813 Endemic Cyprinodont *Aphanius iberus* in Mediterranean Brackish
814 Ponds. *Water*., 12, 3264.
- 815 Shadrin NV, Anufriieva EV. 2020. Structure and trophic relations in hypersaline
816 environments. *Biol Bull Rev*. 10:48-56.
- 817 Sim LL, Davis JA, Strehlow K, McGuire M, Trayler KM, Wild S, Papas PJ, O’Connor
818 J. 2013. The influence of changing hydroperiod on the invertebrate
819 communities of temporary seasonal wetlands. *Freshw Sci*. 32:327–342.
- 820 Souffreau C, Vanormelingen P, Sabbe K, Vyverman W. 2013. Tolerance of resting cells
821 of freshwater and terrestrial benthic diatoms to experimental desiccation and
822 freezing is habitat-dependent. *Phycologia* 52(3):246-255.
- 823 Strayer DL, Findley SEG. 2010. Ecology of freshwater shore zones. *Aquat Sci*. 72:127–
824 163.
- 825 Tang FH, Lenzen M, McBratney A, Maggi F. 2021. Risk of pesticide pollution at the
826 global scale. *Nat Geosci*. 14(4):206-210.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 827 Tuytens K, Vanschoenwinkel B, Waterkeyn A, Brendonck L. 2014. Predictions of
828 climate change infer increased environmental harshness and altered
829 connectivity in a cluster of temporary pools. *Freshw Biol.* 59(5):955-968.
- 830 Valls L, Castillo-Escrivá A, Gómez E, Gil-Delgado JA, Mesquita-Joanes F, Armengol
831 X. 2017. Differential endozoochory of aquatic invertebrates by two duck
832 species in shallow lakes. *Acta Oecologica-Internat. J. Ecol.* 80(1):39-46.
- 833 Van de Leemput I, Dakos V, Scheffer M, van Nes E. 2018. Slow Recovery from Local
834 Disturbances as an Indicator for Loss of Ecosystem Resilience. *Ecosystems.* 21
835 (1):141-152
- 836 Van den Brink PJ, Boxall AB, Maltby L, Brooks BW, Rudd MA, Backhaus T, ... Apitz
837 SE. 2018. Toward sustainable environmental quality: Priority research
838 questions for Europe. *Environ Toxicol Chem.* 37(9):2281-2295.
- 839 Van Geest GJ, Coops H, Scheffer M, Van Nes EH. 2007. Long transients near the ghost
840 of a stable state in eutrophic shallow lakes with fluctuating water levels.
841 *Ecosystems.* 10: 37–47
- 842 Vanschoenwinkel B, Seaman MT, Brendonck L. 2010. Hatching phenology, life history
843 and egg bank size of fairy shrimp *Branchiopodopsis* spp. (Branchiopoda,
844 Crustacea) in relation to the ephemerality of their rock pool habitat. *Aquat*
845 *Ecol.* 44: 771-780.
- 846 Vega-Pozuelo, R. 2018. [Temporary wetlands and saltworks of mid-basin of
847 Guadalquivir river (Spain)]. Doctoral Thesis. Spain: University of Córdoba.
848 Spanish. URI: <http://hdl.handle.net/10396/17027>.
- 849 Walker B, Holling CS, Carpenter SR, Kinzig A. 2004. Resilience, adaptability and
850 transformability in social-ecological systems. *Ecol Soc.* 9(2):5.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 851 Vidal N, Yu J, Gutierrez MF, Teixeira de Mello F, Tavsanoğlu ÜN, Çakiroğlu AI, He
852 H, Meerhoff M, Brucet S, Liu Z, Jeppesen E. 2021. Salinity shapes food webs
853 of lakes in semiarid climate zones: a stable isotope approach. *Inland Waters*. 1-
854 16.
- 855 Walls SC, Barichivich WJ, Brown ME. 2013. Drought, Deluge and Declines: The
856 Impact of Precipitation Extremes on Amphibians in a Changing Climate.
857 *Biology*. 2:399-418.
- 858 Wassens S, Walcott A, Wilson A, Friere R. 2013. Frog breeding in rain-fed wetlands
859 after a period of severe drought: implications for predicting the impacts of
860 climate change. *Hydrobiologia*. 708: 69–80.
- 861 Waterkeyn A, Grillas P, Vanschoenwinkel B, Brendonck L. 2008. Invertebrate
862 community patterns in Mediterranean temporary wetlands along hydroperiod
863 and salinity gradients. *Freshw Biol*. 53(9):1808-1822.
- 864 Waterkeyn A, Vanschoenwinkel B, Elsen S, Anton-Pardo M, Grillas P, Brendonck L.
865 2010a. Unintentional dispersal of aquatic invertebrates via footwear and motor
866 vehicles in a Mediterranean wetland area. *Aquat Conserv Mar Freshw Ecosyst*.
867 20:580–587.
- 868 Waterkeyn A, Vanschoenwinkel B, Grillas, Brendonck L. 2010b. Effect of salinity on
869 seasonal community patterns of Mediterranean temporary wetland crustaceans:
870 A mesocosm study. *Limnol Oceanog*. 5(4):1712-1722.
- 871 Waterkeyn A, Vanschoenwinkel B, Vercampt H, Grillas P, Brendonck L. 2011. Long-
872 term effects of salinity and disturbance regime on active and dormant
873 crustacean communities. *Limnol Oceanog*. 56(3):1008-1022.
874 <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.2011.56.3.1008>

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 875 Williams WD. 1998. Salinity as a determinant of the structure of biological
876 communities in salt lakes. *Hydrobiologia*. 381:191-201.
- 877 Williams DD. 2006. *The Biology of Temporary Waters*. Oxford University Press,
878 Oxford, U.K.
- 879 Zacharias I, Zamparas M. 2010. Mediterranean temporary ponds. A disappearing
880 ecosystem. *Biodiver Conserv*. 19: 3827-3834.
- 881 Yılmaz G, Çolak MA, Özgencil IK, Metin M, Korkmaz M, Ertuğrul S, Soyluer M,
882 Bucak T, Tavşanoğlu UN, Özkan K, Akyürek Z, Beklioğlu M, Jeppesen E.
883 2021. Decadal changes in size, salinity, nutrient levels and biota in lakes in the
884 Konya Plain, Turkey subjected to increasing water abstraction and climate
885 change. *Inland Waters* (this issue).
- 886 Zadereev E, Lipka O, Karimov B, Krylenko M, Elias V, Pinto IS, ... Mader A. 2020.
887 Overview of past, current, and future ecosystem and biodiversity trends of
888 inland saline lakes of Europe and Central Asia. *Inland Waters*. 1-15.
889 10.1080/20442041.2020.1772034.
- 890 Zeng Z, Liu J, Savenije HHG. 2013. A simple approach to assess water scarcity
891 integrating water quantity and quality. *Ecol Ind*. 34:441-449.
- 892 Zohary T, Ostrovsky I. 2011. Ecological impacts of excessive water level fluctuations in
893 stratified freshwater lake. *Inland Waters* 1:47–59.
- 894
895
896 Figure caption.
897 Figure 1. Connexions among drivers, thematic blocks and the solutions discussed in the
898 workshop with (-) negative and (+) positive impacts.

Figure 1. Connexions among drivers, thematic blocks and the solutions discussed in the workshop with (-) negative and (+) positive impacts.

Graphical abstract caption.

 Schematic representation on wetlands threats and challenges. Wetlands' wet and dry phases affected by multiple stressors over time. The emergency in protecting these ecosystems on faces the gaps in knowledge, in actions and in effective regulations.